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Numerical Simulation of Fatigue Crack Propagation in Marine Hydrokinetic Turbines for Increased Reliability and Component Performance

Jeevan Sneha Sakthivel^a, Andrew Ziccarelli^a

^aNorth Carolina State University, Raleigh, 27606, USA

Abstract

This research involves numerical simulation of fatigue crack propagation using finite element analysis to model the behavior of Marine Hydrokinetic Turbines (MHT) under cyclic loading. The analyses take into account the material properties, geometry, and loading conditions of the turbine. A computational approach to simulate fatigue crack propagation in fiber-reinforced composite material was implemented into an analysis program and was then validated. The approach was then used to simulate the response of an MHT blade subjected to realistic loading conditions located off the coast of North Carolina.

Keywords: Marine Hydrokinetic Turbine; Fatigue; Crack Propagation

1. Introduction

Marine hydrokinetic turbines (MHT) generate clean renewable energy from the ocean which helps in providing a promising amount of electricity, while reducing dependence on fossil fuels. These devices harness the energy from ocean currents to generate electricity. However, during this process, the turbines are subjected to harsh marine environments and are subjected to cyclic loading. These conditions may result in fatigue crack initiation and propagation, particularly at locations where the turbine blade tapers in thickness (referred to as ply drops). Fatigue cracks compromise the structural integrity of MHTs, which may ultimately reduce their performance. Development of numerical methods to simulate fatigue crack propagation in MHTs will enable stakeholders to more accurately assess their reliability and remaining lifetime.

Crack initiation and propagation may be modeled in detailed structural finite element analyses (FEA) through the use of the cohesive zone model (CZM). The CZM approach employs cohesive elements, which are specialized finite elements located along a plane of crack propagation, and which open according to a specified traction-separation relationship (TSR). The TSR is governed by the fracture response of the material. Many TSRs have been proposed to simulate crack propagation in fiber-reinforced composites, which are the materials typically used to construct MHT blades. For this project, the TSRs for unidirectional and cyclic loading as described in Turon et al (2007a,

2007b), which were implemented into ABAQUS by Smeets (2019), were utilized. The model was implemented through the user-defined material feature available in ABAQUS.

The finite element model of a simple validation specimen is presented in Figure 1. The implementation of the cohesive zone model was validated by comparing results of simulations with this specimen to benchmark data presented in Krueger (2008) and Krueger (2010). The results from the simulations closely matched the benchmark data, providing confidence that the CZM was correctly implemented and may be used for further analysis.

Figure 1. Simple validation specimen with cohesive zone elements highlighted in red.

2. Simulation of fatigue crack propagation in MHT blades

After implementing the CZM, the next step in the project was to simulate fatigue crack propagation in an MHT blade subjected to realistic loading conditions. To accomplish this, a case study was performed on a representative MHT located off the coast of North Carolina. The case study consisted of three steps: (1) selection of a representative MHT design, (2) calculation of the loads on the turbine blade using Blade Element Momentum Theory and (3) simulation of the blade response including fatigue crack propagation.

The details of the MHT selected as the representative design in the case study are presented in Bir et al. (2011). Design parameters are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Turbine Specifications

Number of rotors	3
Rotor diameter	20 m
Maximum rotor speed	11.5 rpm
Control type	Variable pitch
Free flow velocity	1.5 m/s
Primary blade hydrofoil	NACA 63-424

Loads on the turbine blade were calculated using Blade Element Momentum Theory (BEMT), which is a classical method of calculating loads on a rotating turbine blade. A MATLAB script was developed in order to calculate the loads applied to the blade. The input variables to the analysis were flow velocity, fluid density, turbine rotational speed and the geometry of the blade itself. Once the loads applied to the blade were calculated, a simple structural analysis was performed in order to calculate the bending moment distribution along the length of the blade in the flapwise and edgewise directions, as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Bending moment distribution along length of blade (blue – flapwise, orange – edgewise)

After calculating the bending moment distribution along the blade, the final step in the case study is to calculate the strain at key points along the length of the blade, and use these calculated strains as boundary conditions to a detailed finite element model which includes the CZM to model fatigue crack propagation. One such model, which represents a ply drop location on the blade, is shown in Figure 3a. Results from a preliminary analysis are presented in Figure 3b, where the number of fatigue loading cycles is plotted along the horizontal axis, and the length of the fatigue crack “L1” is plotted on the vertical axis.

Figure 3. Detailed analysis (a) finite element model of ply drop with cohesive zone elements highlighted in red and (b) plot of crack length as a function of loading cycles

3. Continuing and Future Work

The modelling approach will be expanded in the future to incorporate variability in many of the input parameters, including current velocity, blade size and material properties. Future work will also incorporate the effect of saltwater-saturated material on component performance.

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